

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

ОТНОЛОГИЯ МЕТАФОРЫ – РАЗУМ СВЕТА, ОТКРОВЕНИЕ И ΜΑΝΙΑΣ В МАНИХЕЙСТВЕ

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ONTOLOGY OF METAPHOR – LIGHT MIND, REVELATION AND ΜΑΝΙΑΣ IN MANICHAISM

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена изучению Нуса или Разума Света в манихейской традиции. Манихейский дискурс представляет собой многоуровневое пространство языковой игры, содержащее множество гиперссылок, сложных образов и комплексных метафор. Одной из таких метафор, призванных объяснить суть передачи Откровения является образ Разума Света, встречающийся как в коптских, так и в восточных (среднеперсидских, тюркских, согдийских, китайских) манихейских текстах. Философской рефлексии Первоначала откровения как отдельного онтологического уровня в манихейской традиции, ранее не проводилось. Для понимания роли образа Разума Света в манихейской космологии с одной стороны, и всей ближневосточной философской традиции – с другой, необходимо изучить особые принципы манихейской герменевтики, представленные, в первую очередь, в «Кефалайе». Одним из основных принципов выступает метафора, как основа онтологического дискурса. Изучение метафоры Разума Света, ее связей с античной философией, иудео-христианским гнозисом, зороастрийской традицией, поможет избежать предвзятости, закрепившейся за манихейством в академической традиции, отказывающей религии Мани в философском содержании.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of Nus or the Light Mind in the Manichaean tradition. Manichaean discourse is a multi-level space of language game, containing many hyperlinks, complex images and complex metaphors. One of such metaphors, designed to explain the essence of the transmission of Revelation, is the image of the Mind of Light, found both in Coptic and Eastern (Middle Persian, Turkic, Sogdian, Chinese) Manichaean texts. Philosophical reflection on the origin of revelation as a separate ontological level in the Manichaean tradition has not been carried out before. To understand the role of the image of the Light Mind in the Manichaean cosmology, on the one hand, and the entire Middle Eastern philosophical tradition, on the other, it is necessary to study the special principles of the Manichaean hermeneutics, presented, first of all, in *Kephalaia*. One of the main principles is metaphor as the basis of ontological discourse. The study of the metaphor of Light Mind, its connections with ancient philosophy, Judeo-Christian gnosis, the Zoroastrian tradition, will help to avoid the bias that has been entrenched in Manichaeism in the academic tradition, which denies Mani's religion in philosophical content.

Ключевые слова: онтология, метафора, манихейство, Кефалайя, Нус, Разум Света.

Keywords: ontology, metaphor, Manichaeism, Kephalaia, Nus, Light Mind.

The study of Manichaeism as a separate religious and philosophical discipline is one of the main goals of our study. Various concepts of the Manichaean tradition were previously considered in the context of cultural borrowings from Greek philosophy, Judeo-Christian or Zoroastrian traditions, which confused the research perspective. The use of such an analytical approach invariably led to the understanding of the fundamental elements of the Manichaean doctrine through the prism of other discourses. Such a reading inevitably led to a distortion of the perception of the Manichaean discourse as “secondary” in relation to its sources. Thus, the Manichaean system acted as a refrain of those traditions from the point of view of which it was considered by researchers. Throughout the history of the study of Manichaeism by academic science, starting with Isaac de Bospor and Ferdinand Bauer, a number of stable attitudes have been formed in the study of

Manichaeism. The first denied Mani and his followers originality - most of the fundamental concepts of their teaching were considered at best in terms of a chain of borrowings. Another stable narrative is the gradual displacement of the study of Manichaeism into the sphere of historical and religious disciplines, beyond the bounds of philosophical reflection.

Of modern scholars, Baur was the first to propose the use of the term "Manichaean philosophy", in the sense that late antique authors, for example, Alexander of Lycopolis, endowed it with. The involvement of medieval Arabic sources, in particular, *Fihrist* al-Nadim, allowed researchers to speak more confidently not only about Manichaean borrowings from the ancient tradition in the field of religion, but also about some influence of Hellenistic philosophy. This, based on the analysis of *Fihrist*, was stated, in particular, by Gustav Flügel.

In the twentieth century, many Manichaean archives were discovered, their distribution is extraordinary - from Algeria to China. In particular, it is worth mentioning four archaeological expeditions organized by the Berlin Ethnographic Museum in Turfan from 1904 to 1914 under the leadership of Albert Grünwedel and Alfred von le Coq. The study of the cave temples of Dunhua by Mark Aurel Stein and Paul Pelliot belongs to the same period. The discovery of caches with manuscripts in Pahlavi, Sogdian, Uighur and Chinese made it possible to reconstruct the Manichaean hymns, *Shapurakan* and *Huastuanift*. The first edition of *Huastuanift* by Alfred le Coq belongs to the same period. Based on published works, as well as summarizing excerpts from ancient sources known at that time, F. Burkitt in 1925 published the work *The Religion of the Manichaeans* [11], which determined the vector of research into Manichaeism for many years. As a specialist in the New Testament, Burkitt argued that Manichaeism was a Christian heresy, although its origins varied. Another important discovery that radically changed our understanding of Manichaeism was the discovery of Coptic versions of the Manichaean texts by Chester Beatty and Carl Schmidt in 1930. The Coptic versions of many treatises are the most complete, in particular, it is in the Coptic version that one of the main books of Manichaeism, *Kephalaia*, which we will repeatedly refer to in our study, has been almost completely preserved.

The opening of the archives made it possible to partially reconstruct the teachings of Mani, that unique, symbolic language that acted as a universal means of communication throughout Eurasia in late antiquity. As new sources were studied, researchers spoke less and less about Manichaean philosophy, preferring to call the system of the teacher Mani a "mythological structure." If in the mid-1920s Hans Schroeder spoke of the philosophical system of Mani, presented in the critical treatise of Alexander from Likopolis, then Jacob Polotsky [22, pp 699-714] considered the "sensory element" to be the basis of Manichaeism, and the Manichean doctrine a complex construct of images. His programmatic article of 1935 is fundamentally important for our study, since for the first time in the scientific tradition the importance of metaphor for the Manichaean doctrine is emphasized. Insisting on the importance of Eastern traditions, G. Wiedengren develops a hypothesis that Manichaeism is nevertheless a consequence of the development of the Zoroastrian tradition [24]. This allows us to move away from the usual in the Western tradition of the installation of the Judeo-Christian origins of Manichaeism and turn to the complex symbolic system of Zoroastrian Iran. Recognizing the importance of the Zoroastrian construct, however, Wiedengren denied Manichaeism a philosophical content.

The problem of Nous in Manichaeism is the subject of a separate volume in the Manichaean studies series, where for the first time attempts were made to study the image of the Light Mind in Manichaeism on the basis of all the sources at our disposal. However, although A. Böhlig draws parallels with the Greek philosophical tradition, there has been no philosophical reflection on the Manichaean Nus [10, pp 243-264].

Overcoming this bias, which dates back to the first centuries of the Christian era, is one of the grandiose tasks of anyone who embarks on the study of the Manichaean heritage. The study of the Manichaean discourse not from the point of view of polemicists, not in the context of a chain of borrowings, but as an integral system that grasps being in its manifestation, requires a special kind of revision of our numerous sources. Such a revision needs *destruction* in the form in which Heidegger understood it - an appeal to ontological foundations, "where the very essence is hidden" [19, p 22]. On the one hand, it is necessary to avoid the concept of historicism, which builds a topic in which the foundations of discourse are insignificant, less noticeable and less weighty than subsequent layers. On the other, it is worth considering that the forms of representation of the Manichaean discourse are different from the usual metaphysical systems of the West, and this difference should not mislead us. Despite the grandiose shifts of postmodernism and, as a result, the search for "non-ontological philosophical systems", primarily in the Middle East, the separation of metaphysics and poetics, the space of revelation and ontological dogma still prevails in philosophical discourse. If discourse does not respect certain dogmatic premises, it cannot be considered metaphysical, and falls into the realm of poetics or "pre-philosophy".

"Mavias" as a discourse construction principle

The complexity of the Manichaean concept lies in the interweaving of numerous discourses. Thus, in the text of one of the most important books of Manichaeism, *Kephalaia*, the discourse itself unfolds in many dimensions, sometimes following from the end to the beginning, dooming the reader to a hermeneutic odyssey. So, for example, in the essence of a follower's childish question, why a person sees his reflection in water upside down, in the 101st chapter of *Kephalaia* launches complex cosmological reasoning about the roots of the zodiac and connection with heavenly archetypes. The question in chapter 37 about the ways of human greetings refers us to the various ways in which the good archetypes ascend and descend, while, on the contrary, questions of a cosmological nature make Mani talk about the anatomy and ways of organizing the community. Moreover, the basis of this is the play of consonances and associations, understandable only to those included in a certain discursive sphere.

Manichaean texts are an endless space of language play and uncertainty. The complex cosmological system is universal in its essence - it fits into the framework of both the ancient worldview, allowing the Manichaeans to preach in the circles of Hellenistic intellectuals, and the dualistic structure of Iranian religions. Such universalism is largely achieved through the ambiguity of the key elements of the discourse, each of which represents a hermeneutic provocation. The Manichaean sermon addressed to the uninitiated is a provocation that prompts action. J. Coyle examines in detail the various aspects of this provocation, comparing the labels "ab extra" and "ab intra" [12, pp 3-37]. For us, the label attached to Manichaeism by Alexander of Lykopolis is especially important: "the crazy and confused

teachings of Mani.” He rejects any philosophical background in Manichaeism. This thesis was later taken up by Christian authors. We can mention Eusebius of Caesarea, accusing Mani of insanity (μανείς) [4, p.210] derived from μαινόμεαι, a special kind of prophetic frenzy, akin to the gift of the Pythia [15, p 79]. The list of authors who condemn the "possession" (μανιας) of the Manicheans, and even deduce their self-name from "madness", is long. Suffice it to mention the Acts of Archelai [1], Eusebius of Caesarea [4], Leo I, Titus of Bostra [6], Theodoret of Cyrus [8], Augustine of Hippo[3], Timothy of Constantinople. A large body of Syrian polemical literature, starting with Ephraim the Syrian, also uses this narrative.

At a certain point, the appeal to the possession of the Manicheans becomes the leitmotif of the Christian anti-Manichean controversy. For example, in anonymous "Message against Manichaeans" said: "We can easily conclude that the Manichaeans are filled with such madness; especially since this" [2, p 39]. Here it is necessary to briefly mention the meaning given by the ancient Greeks to the term μανιας. Suffice it to recall an episode from Plato's Phaedrus 265b, in which Socrates states: "And frenzy is of two kinds: one is the result of human diseases, the other is a divine deviation from what is usually accepted." [5, p 117]. And further, as a logical conclusion, he divides the "divine deviation" into several types, among which are the Apollo-inspired divination and the poetic inspiration of the Muses. Divine obsession, contact with another world is always twofold - it is enough to recall the motif of the "Apollonic gift" in Greek mythology.

Such rhetoric leads us to the topic of hierophany, interaction with higher powers, going beyond the limits of human nature, like Ajax speaking in a fit of madness in an unknown language, which observers comment on as "the evil god ... taught him, and not the mortal mind of man." [15, p. 82]. Approximately about the same, in the context of Mani, Eusebius of Caesarea says: "Ἐν τούτῳ καὶ ὁ μανείας τὰς φρένας ἐπόνυμος τε τῆς δαιμονώσεως αἰρέσεως τὴν τοῦ λογισμοῦ παρατροπὴν καθωπλιζέτο, τοῦ δαίμονος, αὐτοῦ δὴ τοῦ θεομάχου, σατανᾶ, ἐπὶ λύμῃ πολλῶν τῶν ἄνδρα προβεβλημένου" [4, p 211]. The "perverted mind" is the weapon with which Mani armed himself, his teaching is a product of the human mind, driven by an alien and incomprehensible force, which makes it especially dangerous for an orthodox Christian.

Apollonian prophecy implies knowledge of hidden secrets, or insight into the future, but always ends tragically for the bearer of this gift. This is contact with the world of knowledge that surpasses human understanding, destroying the boundaries of the human "self". This is a kind of symbolic death of the "self", which is hinted at by the common folk etymology of the name Apollo as "destructive". Prophetic madness, close to poetic inspiration, does not leave space for the human nature, the bearer of the gift, like the Pythia, becomes the vessel of the deity, as Eusebius of Caesarea also speaks of: "Βάρβαρος δῆτα τὸν βίον αὐτῷ λόγῳ καὶ πρόπῳ τὴν τε φύσιν δαιμονικός τις ὢν καὶ μανιώδης" [4, p 211]. Mani would be a demon by na-

ture. The adoption of a demonic, divine nature that displaces all sorts of human traits is a phenomenon familiar to ancient culture, it is worth recalling the Greek "ἐνθουσιάζω", "possessed by God". In this state, a person becomes only a carrier of the divine essence, prophesying on behalf of the celestial and, even, in his voice. In a study of the perception of the Manicheans by Syrian Christian authors, J. Coyle quotes from Epiphanius of Salamis, who mentions the origin of the name Mani from Aramaic "ܡܢܝܐ" "vessel", which in Greek is consonant with the word "μανιας". And this etymology, which arose on the play of consonances, in fact quite successfully reflects the essence of the Manichaean teaching [12, p. 11]. On the one hand, this term, "vessel, receptacle" is an important element of the Manichaean ontology, designed to clearly illustrate the principle of interaction between the soul and the body. The body is the seat of the soul, its vessel. On the other, the image of an empty vessel that receives a revelation leads to associations with the Apollonian gift of divination, "obsession with the gods." Such parallels between Apollonian madness and Manichaean prophecy are hardly accidental.

Is it worth considering the epithets assigned by Christian polemics to be only rhetorical clichés? Is it enough to consider the "madness" of the Manichaean doctrine in the eyes of Christian apologists as a synonym for "alien" and "foreign"?

The chain of associations with the Apollonian gift, still a familiar symbolism for Greek-speaking authors of the last centuries of antiquity, indicates that the chosen terms applied to the Manichaeans are not accidental. It can be assumed that they are the result of a deliberate provocation, the ultimate goal of which is to involve the opponent in the discursive space. It is this technique that can be considered one of the main methods of Manichaean proselytism. Thus, addressing the Roman intellectuals, the Western Manichaean preachers were guided by the categories of rationalism, operating with quotes from Cicero. The discursive element, the provocation, was an appeal to the reason and logic of Mani's teachings. On the other hand, in the Christian environment, the argument of "another gospel" was used. This gospel mentioned the hidden nature of Mani's revelation, continuing the prophetic mission of Christ. Skillfully playing on the confrontation between Mazdeism and Zurvanism in Iran, the Manichaeans proposed a dualistic system, on the one hand temporal, emphasizing the importance of Zurvan -Time as a cosmocrator and inheriting the three-part division of Zoroastrian history, and on the other hand, they explained the true nature of Light, the most important ontological construct of Mazdeism. The list of examples goes on. What is important for us is that each of these elements, approaches to involvement in the discursive space, belonged to completely different symbolic systems and could only exist in the multidimensional space of the Middle Eastern language game. Nagel's assumptions about the split in the Manichaean movement and its various branches in the West and East seem logical, although they do not cancel the main thesis: Manichaeism is a boundless space of hermeneutic provocation.

Using the word “*provocation*”, it is necessary to concretize this term, subject it to “destruction”. On the one hand, it is the “provocation” used in numerous Manichaean texts in the form of the “Call” that is a grandiose ontological construct that explains the principle of the emanation of light entities. For example, one of the first passages of *Kephalaia* in 1, 4, 15 explains the importance of the Call as a connecting chain of the world of matter and the world of ideal entities: “Then the First Man sent his Call from [the abyss.] Then the Living Spirit was sent; he descended and brought the First Man out of the abyss.” [7, p. 15] This is an appeal to the Other, an appeal from within the discourse to the world beyond it, a call for help. Like the First Man, Faustus of Mileve appeals to Augustine with a call, a provocation, to discuss the Manichaean doctrine in order to see the truth together [9, p.68].

In the context of discourses so radically different from Western metaphysics, it is provocation from Latin “pro” - “forward” and “voco” meaning “to convene” seem to be the most appropriate way to transcend discursive boundaries. *Provocatio* is one of the cornerstones of Roman criminal law, according to Cicero. This is a call for support, “*provoco ad populum*”, when citizens, primarily plebeians, are involved in the trial as support for the accused. *Provoco* - a call to the people for approval, just like a *decimvir* arrested in a private case *Appius Claudius*, realizing the injustice of the accusations made, appeals to the Roman people. Similarly, the *provocatio* was used as an appeal to the inhabitants of a non-Roman city for the purpose of recognizing Roman citizenship. Of course, the call “*provoco ad populum*” guaranteed maximum protection for the persecuted, it is enough to recall how the appeal to the “voice of the people” radically changed the course of the litigation between *L. Papirius Cursor* and *C. Fabius Maximus Rullian* in 325 BC.

Discussion of litigation at a national assembly is a conscious departure into a changeable discursive space, the sphere of discussion. This is a call for a revision of ideological attitudes, for the transition from the dogma of the law to the *life-world* (*Lebenswelt*) of the individual - the space of rhetoric and poetics. In it, persuasiveness and compliance with the semantic principles of the *life-world* is tantamount to justice, which may run counter to the dogma of the law. In other words, a call for provocation is a call to feel, to feel the tension of being, to “grab” it in its givenness – “here and now”.

In the case of Manichaeism, an appeal to the fundamental dogmas of a particular doctrine is a provocation, followed by a gradual involvement in a multi-level discursive space, an entrance into a labyrinth of meanings and references. Like an appeal to the vital world of the participants in a popular assembly invited to court, the Manichaean polemicists insist not on dogma, but on sensuality. The hypostases of various mythological characters are either combined into one essence, or divided into many separate images that act independently of each other, and then again correlate with their original source.

The text of Christian revelation or Zoroastrian book wisdom is perceived as a sensual metaphor sub-

ject to various reading and perception options. Sensuality, variability, fluidity of discourse - all this brings us back to the problem of *μανιας*. The infinite set of meanings of a thing is alien to the Aristotelian understanding of the name as inherent in only one specific object. Aristotle banishes metaphor from logic, and consequently from metaphysics, assigning to it the realm of rhetoric and poetics, the sphere of Apollonian obsession. For Aristotle, as well as for subsequent European metaphysics, metaphors are meaningless decorations that do not add anything significant to the description of a thing, while for the Middle Eastern discourse it is precisely the maneuvering between many metaphors that is the process of “grasping” being. The more complex and complex the concept, the more multifaceted the metaphor, and the more ways it can be read and interpreted. No wonder, in *Kephalaia* Mani states: “N[o]w, when the apostle will be raised up to the heights, he / and his church, and they depart from the world; at t[h]at instant/ another apostle shall besent to it, to another ch/u[r]ch ...] it [...] Yet, first, he shall make the forms of his church free in the heights, / as I have told you. when [...]; / again, he too shall come down and appear [... / ... and he releases his church and saves it from the flesh [of/ sin ...]” [7, p. 18]. Each of the revelations - Zoroastrian, Buddhist, Christian - are just different readings of the same metaphor, perceived differently by the listeners.

Poetics is likened to hierophany, since it is the only way to interact with the polyphony of meanings, signs and symbols that form the hypertext of revelation. Ricoeur called it “split reference” or, in Handelman's reading, “metaphorically to see like is to appreciate 'the same' within and in spite of 'difference'; “to be like” means both “to be” and “not to be” at the same time” [18, p.36]. This tension gives rise to an ambivalent state of being - the world is viewed as a metaphor for the prototype, ideal archetypes that are outside the temporal space, in the state “before creation”, on the one hand, and as a teleologically conditioned reality, on the other. Thus, the sensory perception of the plurality of *topoi*, the attitude to the world as a metaphor and the absence of axioms that do not allow building a metaphysical topic in the spirit of Aristotle, brought the Manichaean revelation to a Western observer into a frightening space of poetics bordering on madness. This was the “weapon of the demonic mind of Mani”, which Eusebius of Caesarea speaks of. Let us recall the passage of Derrida, stating that Greek metaphysics does not tolerate the principle of chance and does not recognize the negative fundamental principle of things [13, p.11]. On a superficial reading of the Manichaean doctrine, it may seem that there is no place for chance in it either, but creation itself is the result of error, just like the main cosmological events are the result of chance, especially in the sublunar world associated with the evil forces of the zodiacs and archons. Their chaotic nature, inspired by matter, is the sphere of fate, chance. Chance is fatal, but is inextricably linked with the very space of the language and, first of all, the sign. It can be recalled that the root of the word “*fatum*” itself is derived from “*fārī*”, “to speak” or “predict” - fate becomes fate when

it is verbalized, clothed in a sign. One can quote Derida: "Relation to the presence of the present as a complete form of being and ideality is a movement by which I cross the boundaries of empirical existence, facticity, contingency, world, etc., ... I have a strange and unique conviction that that this universal form of presence, since it does not concern any particular being, will not be influenced by it. The relation to my death (to my disappearance in general) is thus hidden in this definition of being as presence, ideality, absolute possibility of repetition. Thus, the possibility of a sign is this relation to death. The definition and destruction of the sign in metaphysics is the concealment of this relation to death, which, nevertheless, produced a meaning" [13, p.51]. While non-metaphysical systems offer the manifestation of a sign as a given, as a manifestation of the Other outside the human "Self".

Poetics of the Light Mind. Between neoplatonic νοῦς and Zoroastrian Wahman

And here we come to a fundamentally important point explaining the principle of the Manichean *μῆνιας* - the interaction of the individual with the world of archetypes or prototypes. In addition, he wonderfully illustrates the interweaving of many levels of discourse in the Manichaean tradition. This is the concept of Nus, the Light Mind, a key element of Manichaean soteriology and epiphany, found in virtually all Manichaean texts. Thus, in Middle Persian texts he is referred to as *whmn* (*yzd*) or *whmn wzrg* [16, p. 52], in Parthian as *mnwhmyd rwšn*, Sogdian - *mnwhmydrwšn*, *whmn rwšn* [24, p. 95], Aramaic - *hilm*, Coptic - *NOYC*, in Latin - *mens* [10, p.246].

Most researchers agree that Mani did not know the Greek language, but was quite familiar with Hellenic philosophy [25, p.70]. Intermediaries between the Greek tradition and Mani were probably the numerous Marcionite treatises and works of Bardaisan. However, the extent of Mani's interaction with the legacy of the "Aramaic philosopher" has not yet been sufficiently studied. One can only state certain parallels noted in the polemical literature [14, p.252]. Mani takes the intuitive, commonplace terms of Greek philosophy and weaves them into the discursive space of revelation. So, Nus, apparently borrowed by him from the teachings of the middle Platonists, in particular, Numenius of Apamea, acts as a world spirit, guaranteeing the purification and salvation of the world.

According to Numenius of Apamea *νοῦς* is dual. On the one hand, he is identified with the Platonic Absolute as the All-Unity. The first Nus is *eidos* of *eidos*, perfect Fullness, removed from the material world. His other hypostasis, the Second Mind, is apparently close to the Mind of the Neoplatonists - this is a manifestation of plurality in the Absolut. The Second Mind of Numenius is the active aspect of the Absolut, which organizes the material world. On the other hand, an important element - the Second Nus is the principle of the cognizability of the world penetrating the universe. The ability to comprehend the universe allows you to interact with matter and bring it to the likeness of ideas. In other words, the Second Nus by Numenius is a multiplicity that allows person to know and change the material world.

In Manichaeism, of course, the consonance of meanings plays a role - the Greek *νοῦς* and the Persian *yazat* Wahman or Avestan *Vohu Manah*, "Good Thought". It can be said that Nus Numenius of Apamea and Wahman of Pahlavi literature are two poles between which the space of revelation unfolds - the manifestation of the Light Mind in Manichaeism. Influenced by Platonism, Pahlavi texts call Bahman as *mēnōg*, that brings good luck [23, p.64]. In the Middle Persian tradition, *mēnōg* is a separate level of reality, which A. Korben called *mundis imaginabilis* - the world of archetypes, eternally existing images, the space of revelation. On a superficial reading, it might seem that *mēnōg* refers to the eschatological expectations of the world before creation and after the apocalypse. Numerous Late Zoroastrian apocalyptic does bring us to this reading of the term, but it is much more complex. It is devoid of a temporal dimension, since it always manifests itself "here and now" - in various fractures of both macro- and microhistory. So, for example, one of the features of divinity is the ability to exist in two dimensions at the same time - *mēnōg* and *gētīg*, in the likeness of *yazats*. At the same time, entities that are in different worlds are integral, exist, like reflections of the ideal world of archetypes in the space of mixing - the material world. Some righteous people, such as Viraz, could cross the border between these worlds at the time of the revelation. It can be assumed that the very space of revelation is the exit to the ideal world of *mēnōg*. Thus, Wahman is a Thought that exists in an ideal world and descends into the space of limited time, the sublunar world, to fight with matter. He puts on "the veil of time," since only in space, where the Thought is temporally limited, is the onset of the eschatos possible.

In this case, the role that the Light Mind plays in the Manichaean picture of the world is important to us. In most Manichaean texts, there is confusion: he is either an emanation of Jesus, or directly correlates with him. Here we have a multi-level space of metaphor and ambiguity unfolding in front of us, where the Light Mind is identical to Jesus the Splendour, is his emanation and, in turn, itself breaks up into five entities - Reason, Mind, Intelligence, Thought, and Understanding [16.p.52]. He is the messenger in the material world, responsible for the creation and renewal of the true church. It is the Light Mind in the Manichaean tradition that is responsible for the space of revelation and victory over demons through the virtues.

The Light Mind was sent by the Father of Greatness to direct and correct matter with the help of its five emanations, and in this it merges with the image of Jesus the Splendour. On the other hand, it is seen as a power inherent in Jesus, as a refraction of his light nature: "And the first power that he called out is the Light Mind, the father of all the Apostles, the beginning of all churches, the one that Jesus set, like us, in holy church." [7, p.39] The phrase "like us" plays a key role here, since Jesus the Splendour is often seen in the context of the heavenly Double of Mani, his prototype, who appeared in the world. This is the heavenly manifestation of the prophetic mission of the Redeemer, the bearer of gnosis and the savior of the world. The Light Mind here

performs a slightly different function - it is the driving force of prophecy, which has power over matter and is able to awaken light in the realm of darkness, one of the robes of Splendor. In addition, in the Turkic texts, he acts as an angel-protector of the Law, an entity separate from Jesus: "Jesus, Kanig and the God Wahman, the angels that guard the Law, the ... Buddhas that have descended repeatedly" [10, p.244]. In the Psalms, PsB 154.1-21, a parallel is drawn between Jesus as the bridegroom of the soul and the Light Mind as the bridegroom of the Church: "The Bride is the Church, the Bridegroom is the Light Mind. The Bride is the soul, the Bridegroom is Jesus" [17, p.96], he is the personification of revelation, light, clothed in a cover of matter.

Reasoning about the nature of the Light Mind touches on a fundamentally important aspect of the incarnation in Manichaeism - being an unlimited space of revelation, it simultaneously gives light to the Church, as an assembly of the righteous, and fights in every follower. Not without reason, the student asks Mani in the 38th chapter of *Kephalaia*: "I ask you: if he (Mind) is a great god, immutable, immeasurable, how does he come and appear in the smallness of the body?" [7, p.95]. To which Mani replies: "If I follow [[your request,]] explain to you what you insist on, ... I will give sight to those who see; thanks to you, I will make a living spring break out for those who are thirsty, and they will drink and live" [7, pp.95-96].

Thus, the principle of the incarnation as an interaction with the space of the Absolute is the cornerstone of Manichaean soteriology. Like the Pahlavi opposition of Wahman and Akaman, or the Judeo-Christian "New" and "Old" man, the Light Mind humbles matter, providing a new birth. This is an important identification of macrocosm and microcosm - like the cosmic battles between good and evil, the same confrontation unfolds in the human body. This metaphor, however, is not "useless", from the Aristotelian point of view, it leads us to the idea that the opposition in man is just as powerful and destructive as the battles of demons with the Sons of Light. "So also is this body ! A mighty power lives / here, even if it is small in its stature. Nevertheless, s/in dwells within, and the Old man who is lodged in it. Certainly he is cruel, with great cunning; until the Light Mind finds how to humble this body, and drive it [according to] / his pleasure". [7, p.99] Here before us unfolds the global principle of the world as a metaphor, and the metaphor is not linear, identifying several levels of reality - for the cosmic order, all levels are equal. We can see how the Manichaean language game works by a large number of "hyperlinks" in the text. So, to the question about the incarnation, how a small body can accommodate the immortal gods, Mani answers: "Again, look, see ! These gods, in that [... are] great and mighty ones. And each one of them is enclosed and hard pressed] i[n this pl]ace when he is set; like trees / [hol]ding to their taproot. So also this is how each / [o]ne of them has 'held to his taproot' in the world, according to / [the] k[ind] of place in which he is set "[7, p.99].

The image of a tree is one of the key elements of discourse that triggers many possible interpretations and references to other episodes in the text. Moreover,

just as many hypostases, acting independently of each other, are identified with the higher essence that gave birth to them, all chains of associations and references eventually go to the key elements. Firstly, this is an unconditional reference to the key parable of the Manichaean teachings and a quote from the second chapter of *Kephalaia*, the parable of the two trees. In this case, the image of the tree uses a language game - Mani uses the ambiguous term of Greek philosophy for matter, ὕλη, which, when translated literally, means "wood". Then this image is colored with biblical quotes, allusions to the Tree of Knowledge, which, in fact, stands at the origins of material human existence, and the Tree of the Cross, from which the last cosmic epoch is counted, as well as Middle Eastern symbols. So, in the Manichaean tradition, trees are creatures of darkness, since they are connected with the zodiac forces by invisible threads "*likhme*" (or Conduits) and through them the limitations and filth of the starry expanses ooze onto the earth. Likening the gods to trees is a multi-component metaphor that explains both their vocation (like the Trees of Knowledge and the Cross), and their nature (mediators between the outer world and the inner world), and, finally, the inclusiveness in the sub-lunar world, like the inclusiveness of matter- ὕλη.

This passage is an important digression, an implicit explanation not only of the role of the gods, but also of the principle by which sin bound the Soul to the Body. Turnover "hard pressed" illustrates the mixing principle. It is this mixture that does not allow the soul to turn away from the body and turn to the light, for which the Light Mind was sent into the world. "[The] Light / [Mind] comes and finds the soul [... / ...] it assuming it in the [...] its wisdom [... / ...] he shall become for it [... / ...] the bonds [...] / members in the body"[7, p.100]. Further, Mani argues that a person is locked in the bonds of sin, body and matter, and only the acquisition of the Light Mind gives freedom. The disclosure of the universal principle that permeates the universe, gaining freedom through the rejection of the boundaries of one's own "Self", which binds the immortal soul - is a common Gnostic passage. It is important for us to note that the opposition of those elements that are "hard pressed" in the world of matter and free archetypes of the ideal world perfectly illustrate the principle *μᾶνις* of the anti-Manichaean polemicists. An appeal to the ever-manifesting Light Mind is an appeal to a world free from boundaries, removing the separation between the subject and the object, the cognizer and the cognized, and, as a result, between the Tree of Knowledge and the Tree of the Cross.

After the cosmological explication, Mani suddenly proceeds to explain the behavior of the community: if one of the brothers departs from the truth, it is necessary to get together and jointly convince the apostate, appealing to his reason. This is the same provocation, the appeal that we spoke about earlier, appeal to the discursive space in which the ontology of metaphor unfolds. It is provocation in its original, ancient Roman meaning, as an appeal to the voice of the people (in this case, the community), that is the only possibility of healing and liberation. Thus, the strange insertion about

the obscuring of the Mind takes on meaning - it continues the passage about the inclusiveness of metaphor, as a space for freedom of interpretation of the image, metaphor, sermon. Can free interpretation be wrong? According to Mani, no. Since unfreedom is a product of matter, any unfree judgment is wrong. Any free judgment is true insofar as freedom itself is an attribute of the extra-material world. Mani draws to followers communities, describing the role of the Light Mind - "[No one] in the world has given freedom to his children [and his brothers and his kin, and made them free] from the variance of all things, the way I have." [7, p.104]

Light Mind as an ontological principle

Another important element of the doctrine of the Light Mind is its temporality and ultimate individuality. Despite the fact that it is always manifested in the world and permeates the universe, it fights with Sin in every person, for the hierophany of the Light Mind, a temporal and individual dimension is necessary. Time in Manichaeism is a rather complex phenomenon, studied in detail in a number of scientific works [20, p.194], [21, p.111].

Consideration of the problems of time is not within the scope of our tasks, however, it should be noted that time is associated with the final liberation of the world from the bonds of matter. Time is thinning, its run is accelerating, each era, the closer it is to the end of the world, the shorter it is, the shorter the life expectancy and the shorter the period of fulfillment of the prophecies. Each term - a moment, an hour, a day, a month, a year - was created before the appearance of the material world in the form of archetypes and set by the Father of Majesty in the "middle era" to rule the demonic zodiac circle. Each of the five "lords of time" - from a moment to a year is higher than the previous one, a fairly clear hierarchy is formed that fixes them in being. In addition, they are not accidentally called "seals" of time, since they do not allow limited, finite nature to pour out beyond the fences of the material world. Absolute time, devoid of personification - the time of existence of the "middle world", the allotted time for the cosmic confrontation between light and dark nature. The absolute time of the cosmos is refracted in personal time, fixed by "seals", and only having acquired personification, it acquires a real totality. Each individual "lord of time" is responsible for each individual time interval and for the confluence of all time spans necessary to complete the cosmic cycle. Here we have another complex metaphor, in which the extremely limited time, reduced to singularity, is equated with the Absolute time. Each epoch is associated with the manifestation of the Light Mind in a particular Church, headed by a Messenger. Zarathustra and Buddha, Jesus and Mani are the renewers of the gnosis discovered by the Light Mind. It is in the maintenance of the "lamp of revelation" that the ontological task of Nus lies. But why does he incarnate not evenly, choosing the Chosen Ones, and not showing himself to everyone equally? Chapter 102 of *Kephalaia* is devoted to this, translating to the ethical dimension of revelation. Mani claims that human nature could not bear the burden of revelation: "Know that the Light Mind that

dwells in the Chosen Ones can create in believers all the signs and signs that you told me about; but the Chosen Ones could not bear the greatness he would reveal to them. And not only for this reason, but above all for this reason: if he revealed something to the Chosen Ones and they became seers, they would become Apostles, and no one would humble himself before his neighbor" [7, p.261]. In addition, knowing one's term would deprive a person of righteousness and virtues - people's lives would turn into an expectation of a fulfilled term and salvation. The hierarchy is broken, the chains of revelation are interrupted. Cosmology is hierarchized because not everyone is given the gift of prophecy to endure the "Apollinian" gift. Human nature in its ultimate individuality is only a reflection of the heavenly archetypes, which are in an ideal, pre-created state. Therefore, like any similarity or "vessel", it is fragile and subject to the madness of matter. Only the personification of the Light Mind can save the vessel from destruction. Only through the refraction of the Revelation through the Messenger is it possible to endure the weight of the Absolute Light, destructive to matter. This is the principle of "divine possession", which became a constant motive of the anti-Manichean controversy and reflected one of the fundamental things of the Manichean preaching. Salvation from the outside world is possible only in going beyond the limits of the mortal and single "Self". But the limits, the boundaries of matter, by which human existence is compressed, allow him to ascend "like trees" into the sky, to the Absolute. Ultimate personalization provides a vertical topic, aspiration upwards, forms the ascending orientation of the Manichean cosmology.

Conclusions

The metaphor of archetypes, most clearly manifested in the image of the Light Mind and its hypostases, is fundamentally important for understanding the development of all subsequent Middle Eastern philosophical reflection. It is thanks to the connection of the Light Mind as a force penetrating the universe and embodied in every person that one can see the origins of the concept of *Alam al-mithal*, the world of suspended images or the "eighth karshvar" of the Iranian theosophists. Its very name includes an oxymoron. Almost a thousand years after the life of Mani, Yaahya as-Suhrawardī first gave the name to this world - *Nā-Kojā-Abād*, "land of nowhere", the sphere where revelations and visions are born, the space of human fantasy. This is neither the spiritual world nor the physical, it is in tension between the metaphysics of the manifested world and the spheres of the Absolute. Mythical images, revelations of the prophets have their own reality in it, this is a special angle of refraction of the Cosmic Light, which forms a separate level of reality. "Eighth Karshvar"- an illustration of a rebellion against metaphysics, in the words of A. Korben, this is the sphere of pure intuition and insight, the Sign, as such. The world of revelation is inhabited by images and archetypes that are prototypes of the material world. But here you should not draw parallels with Plato's eidos - "Eighth Karshvar" is a projection of the space of perception, and not of Absolute Reality. In other words, like the Manichean Light Mind, which carries the revelation

and renewal of the world, *Alam al mithal* simultaneously reflects the universal order of the universe and is extremely individual - the framework of the "I" of one's own individual interferes with conveying and retelling the experience of perceiving it. To cross the border between subjects, a metaphor is needed, the only means of expressing non-verbalized experience. It, in turn, is part of a complex language game, multilayered and multifaceted, often requiring departure from the ultimate concreteness of being "here and now". Of course, epiphany requires sacrifice, and the victim of Manichaeism was perceived from the outside as "madness", which has become a literary cliché in the Christian tradition. Appeal to the Mind of the Light of Mani and his followers in the sphere of Hellenized thought, as well as Christian patristics, was considered through the prism of poetic madness, alien to the sphere of metaphysics. It was the complex relationship of hierarchization, on the one hand, and the space of uncertainty, the non-significance of metaphor, on the other, that caused rejection and fear. The battle of Light and Darkness, carrying in its very essence uncertainty, and at the same time predetermined from the very beginning, seemed an insoluble, "insane" paradox. And in the paradox, in the metaphor, as a reflection, refraction of many realities, lies the main principle of the unfolding of the Manichaean discourse. A discourse containing a revolt against Aristotelian metaphysics in its very essence.

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